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CoARA Action Plan by the Helmholtz Open Science Office

Action Plan to Implement the Ten Commitments of the Agreement on
Reforming Research Assessment

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Abstract

In February 2025, the Helmholtz Open Science Office signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). This Action Plan describes the role of the Helmholtz Open Science Office in promoting the openness, quality, and impact of research within the Helmholtz Association and shaping the framework conditions that enable this. The Action Plan provides an overview of interplay between open science and research assessment reforms, followed by a description of the status quo and planned activities for 2026 to 2030 based on the ten commitments of the the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment.

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The Helmholtz Open Science Office

Guided by the motto 'Advancing Open Science at Helmholtz and beyond', the Helmholtz Open Science Office supports the Helmholtz Association and its research centers in shaping the cultural change towards open science.¹ With 18 independent Helmholtz Research Centers and around 46,000 employees, the Helmholtz Association is Germany's largest scientific organization. Long-term research programs in six strategic areas address major challenges and pressing issues facing society: Energy; Earth & Environment; Health; Information; Aeronautics, Space and Transport; and Matter.

The Helmholtz Open Science Office supports the Helmholtz Research Centers by shaping a unified Helmholtz-wide approach to open science through the development and harmonization of policies, monitoring progress, supporting sustainable digital infrastructures, rethinking incentive mechanisms, and fostering community-building. The Helmholtz Open Science Office works closely together with different stakeholders (including researchers at various career stages and support staff in service institutions such as libraries, data and computing centers, etc.) from the Helmholtz Research Centers and brings them together in dedicated task groups to advance various aspects of open science.

To increase awareness and knowledge exchange around research assessment reforms and to support and guide the Helmholtz Research Centers in further development of quality-oriented evaluation approaches and criteria, a cross-cutting [Task Group Research Assessment](#) was founded in March 2025 by the Helmholtz Open Science Office and the [Working Group Open Science](#). In addition, a [Task Group Helmholtz Quality Indicators for Data and Software Products](#) guides the development and implementation of new metrics that are intended to increase the visibility and quality of research outputs beyond text publications.

At the national and international level, the Helmholtz Open Science Office collaborates with a broad range of stakeholders to improve the quality and impact of research in the spirit of the Helmholtz mission. The Helmholtz Open Science Office was involved in the development of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment in 2022 and is active as a member in the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) in various of its working groups. Furthermore, the Helmholtz Open Science Office is engaged in several working groups of the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) as well as in the [Open Science Monitoring Initiative \(OSMI\)](#) working group 'Understanding the open science monitoring landscape'. At national level, the Helmholtz Open Science Office actively shapes the initiative 'Digitality in Science' of the Alliance of Science Organizations in Germany, including through its interest group '[Reputation and Incentives](#)'. In February 2025, the Helmholtz Open Science Office signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and joined CoARA. In March 2025, the head of the Helmholtz Open Science Office, Mathijs Vleugel, took over the coordination of the [CoARA National Chapter Germany](#).

¹ Helmholtz Association (2022): Helmholtz Open Science Policy. Version 1.0. Approved in the 119th General Assembly of the Helmholtz Association on 20-21 September 2022.
<https://doi.org/10.48440/os.helmholtz.056>

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Open Science and Research Assessment

There are many aspects that tie together the cultural change towards open science and current efforts to reshape research assessment. These include shared objectives, the stakeholders involved, and the strategies employed to drive sustainable change within a globally connected research ecosystem. This section summarizes where these two movements converge and how they can benefit from one another.

Improving research quality and impact: Research assessment reforms and the open science movement share a number of common goals, most notably their ultimate aim to improve the quality, impact, and trustworthiness of research. Making research processes and outcomes accessible according to FAIR and open science principles is key to this, as it enhances transparency, reproducibility, collaboration, and the overall robustness of research. Providing the right incentives to support these practices not only strengthens scientific integrity but also enables wider reuse within the scientific community and impact in society and policymaking.

Valuing diverse contributions to research: At the same time, expanding the scope of what research outcomes and activities are recognized and rewarded in evaluations allows for (1) more inclusive recognition of the many different contributions to scientific progress and (2) increased transparency throughout the research cycle. By making work, responsibility, and expertise visible beyond traditional publications, this broader approach better reflects how research is actually conducted and incentivizes collaborative and sustainable research practices. For example, publishing outputs beyond traditional journal articles and books provides visibility of contributions such as data collection/analysis/curation, software development, infrastructure maintenance/operation, and peer review. This helps acknowledge the work of researchers with varied profiles and expertise, supports more diverse career paths in science, and promotes reproducibility, reusability and overall research quality.

Recognizing good research practices: Research assessment that values responsible research practices can play a key role in improving the integrity and trustworthiness of science. Good research practices encompass transparent reporting of research processes and outcomes according to FAIR and open science principles. Reforming research assessment to include indicators such as the application of FAIR data principles, the open sharing of research data, code, and methods, the consistent use of persistent identifiers, the preregistration of study designs where appropriate, and the development and implementation of data management plans across the research lifecycle - therefore going beyond traditional research metrics - can be seen as an opportunity to create incentives that support research integrity by enhancing transparency, reproducibility, and accountability of research and its outcomes.²

² Alexander von Humboldt Foundation et al. (2025): The future development of assessment processes for research activity in the context of open science. Discussion paper of the Task Force for Measure 4 of the Alliance 2021-2025 Open Access Strategy as part of the Alliance Initiative 'Digital Information in Science'. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15836010>

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Open research information for fair and transparent assessment: Reliable, open, and machine-readable research information provides a critical foundation for fair and transparent assessment systems. Initiatives such as the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information emphasize the need for open and interoperable metadata to support responsible assessment practices. Making additional elements such as peer review reports, funding information, collaboration networks, and contributor roles openly available further enables nuanced and transparent evaluations of different contributions to research.

Learning from cultural change processes in open science: The open science movement offers valuable insights into how cultural change in the research ecosystem can be achieved. Its progress has been driven by community-led efforts, alignment of values with incentives, and the development of policies, infrastructures, training, and tools that make open practices easier to adopt. Research assessment reforms can build on these lessons: just as open science gained momentum through a combination of grassroots action and institutional support, lasting change in assessment will require both bottom-up and top-down commitment from similar stakeholders.

CoARA Commitments: Status Quo and Planned Actions

This section provides an overview of the ten CoARA commitments, with a description of the current activities and ongoing developments as well as concrete actions by the Helmholtz Open Science Office to advance these within the Helmholtz Association and the wider German research landscape over the timeframe 2026 to 2030.

1. Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research

Status Quo

- ✓ The 2022 [Helmholtz Open Science Policy](#) provides a joint commitment and shared direction of the Helmholtz Research Centers towards open science in accordance with the principle 'as open as possible and as closed as necessary'. It defines specific and measurable objectives and recommended practices to promote high-quality publications, including research data and research software outputs. In the context of research assessment, the Helmholtz Open Science Policy states that Helmholtz will "recognize and value the application of open science practices and, to this end, create incentives for open science practices (open access, open research data, open research software, as well as infrastructures and services)".

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- ✓ A dedicated [Task Group Helmholtz Quality Indicators for Data and Software Products](#) has developed concepts for multidimensional Helmholtz Quality Indicators that can be used to incentivize and recognize high-quality data and software publications based on the FAIR principles and output-type-specific quality criteria.³ The Helmholtz Quality Indicators can be used for qualitative assessment of individual publications as well as for quantitative assessment in the context of institute-level key performance indicators (KPIs).
- ✓ The [Helmholtz Software Award](#) aims to promote the development of professional and high-quality research software and to recognize the commitment to software as the basis of modern data science. The award shines a spotlight on the sustainable development and operation of research software, promoting reusability and collaboration. Prizes are awarded in three categories: 'Scientific Originality Prize', 'Sustainability Prize' and 'Newcomer Prize'.
- ✓ Through a large-scale survey among 1145 Helmholtz researchers, the [Task Group Research Assessment](#) has recently made an inventory of which assessment criteria researchers expect are currently being used versus the criteria they think should be used to evaluate their contributions in the context of hiring and promotion. The survey showed substantial differences between currently perceived criteria and those regarded as important, while also highlighting how priorities differ across research areas and career stages.

Planned Actions

- Based on the concepts for both Helmholtz Quality Indicators, the [Task Group Helmholtz Quality Indicators for Data and Software Products](#) is currently developing automated and semi-automated solutions to facilitate the (partial) extraction of the different quality dimensions and to support Helmholtz-wide adoption of the indicators. These pipelines will be tested for the first time as part of the recurring annual institutional evaluation processes in early 2027. Following this first reporting period, feedback from the relevant stakeholders will be collected to further refine the quality dimensions of the indicators as well as the underlying workflows.
- The [Task Group Research Software](#) is currently in the process of refining the process for the Helmholtz Software Award and improving the transparency and clarity of the process and criteria for both applicants and peer reviewers in line with the CoARA principles. This updated approach will be implemented during the next call for nominations for the Helmholtz Software Award.

³ Task Group Helmholtz Quality Indicators for Data and Software Products of the Working Group Open Science and the Helmholtz Open Science Office (2026): A Framework for Assessing Research Data and Software Publications - The Helmholtz Quality Indicator. Helmholtz Open Science Office.
<https://doi.org/10.48440/os.helmholtz.085>

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- To complement the above survey, the [Task Group Research Assessment](#) is planning to create an inventory of the current formalized criteria in evaluation procedures for individual researchers during hiring and promotion processes. Based on these outcomes, the task group will identify and further develop modular CV templates that include quality-based procedures for evaluating the criteria that were indicated as important by Helmholtz researchers. In addition, the task group will develop recommendations on the responsible use of KPIs in the context of periodical evaluation of the Helmholtz Research Centers, and develop new indicators and qualitative approaches when deemed appropriately
2. **Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators**

Status Quo

- ✓ Quantitative metrics are expected to continue to play a role in research assessment. However, their responsible use must be critically reconsidered in light of their intended purpose and the type and level of evaluation. While metrics typically serve only a supporting function in the assessment of individual researchers, evaluations at the level of research centers typically rely more heavily on KPIs, which are in many cases considered necessary to ensure inter-institutional and longitudinal comparability.

Planned Actions

- The [Task Group Research Assessment](#) plans to create an inventory documenting where publication-based metrics are used in assessments of individual researchers and in center-level evaluations. Where feasible, alternative peer-review-based approaches will be identified, further developed, and promoted. These efforts include the design of CV templates that reduce reliance on narrow metrics and strengthen qualitative evaluation. In cases where quantitative indicators remain unavoidable, the Helmholtz Open Science Office will promote awareness of their limitations and encourage transparent communication about their appropriate use.

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3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index

Status Quo

- ✓ Awareness of the limitations and unintended consequences of assessment criteria that are based on journal- and publication-based metrics appears to be high across the various communities within the Helmholtz Research Centers. Nevertheless, traditional bibliometric indicators are likely to still play a role in some assessment procedures and there seem to be historically-rooted cultural differences between disciplines that are more difficult to overcome.

Planned Actions

- The [Task Group Research Assessment](#) plans to create an inventory documenting in which cases publication-based metrics are still used in assessment procedures for individual researchers and as part of center-level evaluations. Based on these findings, the task group will develop targeted recommendations on how to move away from the inappropriate use of bibliometric indicators, including by providing alternative approaches. These include the identification and further development quality-based evaluation procedures and KPIs for assessing researchers and their organizations.
- It remains necessary to raise awareness of the inappropriate use of bibliometric indicators, even in organizations that have signed DORA and/or CoARA. The Helmholtz Open Science Office will therefore continue to address this issue during events and exchanges at all levels, including researchers, support staff, and higher management.

4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organizations in research assessment

Status Quo

- ✓ The Helmholtz Open Science Office supports moving away from the use of research organization rankings in assessment, in line with the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. In practice, however, many research organizations still use and remain strongly dependent on such rankings. This dependence appears difficult to overcome because rankings are deeply embedded in reputational considerations, funding decisions, and strategic planning. They provide a simple, quantifiable measure that is often perceived as objective, even though they fail to capture the full complexity, diversity, and societal impact of research. Changing these practices requires not only

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alternative assessment approaches but also cultural shifts, policy alignment, and sustained engagement across multiple levels of the research ecosystem. While completely abandoning institutional rankings can raise concerns about potential competitive or reputational risks ('first-mover disadvantage'), experiences from reform-oriented systems, e. g. in the Netherlands, suggest that it may also confer strategic advantages by positioning organizations as leaders in shaping more responsible, inclusive, and future-oriented assessment practices ('first-mover momentum').

Planned Actions

- As a central unit for the Helmholtz Research Centers, the Helmholtz Open Science Office encourages efforts to replace simplistic indicators with approaches that better capture research quality and impact. The Helmholtz Open Science Office advocates for holistic, qualitative, and context-sensitive assessment practices that reflect openness, transparency, and equity, and the Helmholtz Open Science Office is committed to enabling the cultural and structural changes needed for responsible research assessment across all Helmholtz Research Centers. The Helmholtz Open Science Office will continue to (1) raise awareness about the limitations of global university rankings, (2) emphasize institutional rankings should never trickle down into the evaluation of researchers and research projects, and (3) advocate for alternative, qualitative and quantitative approaches to institute-level assessment - including endorsing the INORMS Research Evaluation Group's #MoreThanOurRank initiative.

5. Commit resources to the reform of research assessment as necessary to achieve the organizational changes committed to

Status Quo

- ✓ The Helmholtz Open Science Office has prioritized the reform of research assessment by making it one of its current focus areas. This means that organizational resources are made available in direct support of relevant activities within the Helmholtz Association and participation in national and international initiatives. As part of its commitment to reforming research assessment, two cross-institutional and interdisciplinary Helmholtz expert groups are currently being coordinated by the Helmholtz Open Science Office, namely the [Task Group Research Assessment](#) and the [Task Group Helmholtz Quality Indicators for Data and Software Products](#).
- ✓ The Helmholtz Open Science Office is an active contributor to the work of CoARA, the Open Science Monitoring Initiative, and the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information. At the national level, the Helmholtz Open Science Office is currently the

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coordinator of the CoARA National Chapter Germany and member of the interest group 'Reputation and Incentives' of the Alliance of Science Organizations in Germany.

Planned Actions

- The Helmholtz Open Science Office intends to continue its current high level of activity to support research assessment reforms over the coming years, both within the Helmholtz Association and in support of systemic reforms within the German and international research ecosystems. In order to further expand its activities to drive research assessment reforms, the Helmholtz Open Science Office commits to actively pursuing additional third-party funding.

6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes

Status Quo

- ✓ A dedicated [Task Group Helmholtz Quality Indicators for Data and Software Products](#) has developed concepts for multidimensional Helmholtz Quality Indicators that can be used to incentivize and recognize high-quality data and software publications based on the FAIR principles. The Helmholtz Quality Indicators can be used for qualitative assessment of individual publications as well as for quantitative assessment in the context of institute-level KPIs.
- ✓ Through a large-scale survey among 1145 Helmholtz researchers, the [Task Group Research Assessment](#) has recently made an inventory of which assessment criteria researchers expect are currently being used versus the criteria they think should be used to evaluate their contributions in the context of hiring and promotion. The survey showed substantial differences between currently perceived criteria and those regarded as important, while also highlighting how priorities differ across research areas and career stages.

Planned Actions

- Based on the concepts for both Helmholtz Quality Indicators, the [Task Group Helmholtz Quality Indicators for Data and Software Products](#) is currently developing automated and semi-automated solutions to facilitate the (partial) extraction of the different quality dimensions and to support Helmholtz-wide adoption of the indicators. These pipelines will be tested for the first time as part of the recurring annual institutional evaluation processes in early 2027. Following this first reporting period, feedback from

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the relevant stakeholders will be collected to further refine the quality dimensions of the indicators as well as the underlying workflows.

- To complement the above survey, the [Task Group Research Assessment](#) is planning to create an inventory of the current formalized criteria in evaluation procedures for individual researchers during hiring and promotion processes. Based on these outcomes, the task group will identify and further develop modular CV templates that include quality-based procedures for evaluating the criteria that were indicated as important by Helmholtz researchers. In addition, the task group will develop recommendations on the responsible use of KPIs in the context of periodical evaluation of the Helmholtz Research Centers, and develop new indicators and qualitative approaches when deemed appropriately.

7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Status Quo

- ✓ Regularly organized Helmholtz Open Science Fora are intended to provide an environment where Helmholtz researchers, support staff, and research managers can be informed regarding the latest developments in open science, exchange best practices, address challenges, and progress through mutual learning. As a public and open format, the Helmholtz Open Science Seminars enable contributions from participants beyond Helmholtz. Over the past years, several of these events have been dedicated to [research assessment](#), [open research information](#), [new indicators](#), [CoARA](#), etc.
- ✓ The Helmholtz Open Science Office actively promotes awareness around research assessment reforms by organizing events in the context of the CoARA National Chapter Germany, the interest group 'Reputation and Incentives' of the Alliance of Science Organizations in Germany, and by contributing to public events and internal discussions on research assessment.

Planned Actions

- The Helmholtz Open Science Office intends to continue its current high level of activity to support research assessment reforms over the coming years, both within the Helmholtz Association and in support of the German and international research ecosystem.

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8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition

Status Quo

- ✓ The Helmholtz Open Science Office actively supports and engages in opportunities for mutual learning within CoARA and its working groups, the CoARA National Chapter Germany, the Helmholtz Association, the DORA National and International Initiatives Discussion Group, the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information, the Open Science Monitoring Initiative. In addition, members of the Helmholtz Open Science Office frequently participate in national and international events related to research assessment reforms.

Planned Actions

- The Helmholtz Open Science Office intends to continue its current high level of activity to support research assessment reforms over the coming years, both within the Helmholtz Association and in support of the German and international research ecosystem.

9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the Commitments

Status Quo

- ✓ After joining CoARA, the Helmholtz Open Science Office communicated its commitment through its newsletter, on its website, on social media and during relevant events.
- ✓ By participating in public and internal Helmholtz events, and contributing to national and international conferences, the Helmholtz Open Science Office highlights its progress in the intended research assessment reforms.

Planned Actions

- This CoARA Action Plan will be disseminated via Helmholtz-internal and external communication channels (e. g., Helmholtz Open Science Newsletter, social media channels), through the CoARA National Chapter Germany, and in the context of national and international events.
- The Helmholtz Open Science Office commits to publicly communicating about the progress made on implementing the ten CoARA commitments within 5 years of signing

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the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (e. g., by February 2030 the latest), including a transparent description of the challenges encountered in implementing its planned actions.

10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

Status Quo

- ✓ Progress on the development of the Helmholtz Quality Indicators has been transparently documented³ and communicated with the broader research community at national and international conferences.

Planned Actions

- Feedback on the first implementation of the Helmholtz Quality Indicators will be collected to further refine the indicators and underlying workflows. The complete process, including workflows, training, and lessons-learned will be shared with the research community through publications and presentations within the CoARA membership and other national and international fora.
- Findings by the survey conducted by the [Task Group Research Assessment](#) are expected to provide a solid evidence base on the status quo of research assessment within the Helmholtz Association and the priorities for different subsets of researchers. Survey outcomes and newly developed evaluation procedures and CV templates will be made openly available to the broader research community, as long as they do not compromise confidentiality of the Helmholtz Research Centers and its employees.

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